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Abstract

The project title "A study on marketing of mango in Malda district of west Bengal was carried out under the guidance of Mr. Amit kumar . Malda district was purposely selected due to production of mango is at commercial level . Multi – stage random sampling procedure was followed to select respondents. Out of 15 blocks of Malda district Ratua I block was selected purposely based on Number of respondents was doing Mango farming.10 villages were selected randomly. The number of mango growers interviewed was 100 which were divided into four groups (Marginal, Small, medium and large) later on. The number of respondents were selected randomly in each random 10 villages. A structured schedule was used to collect the data through survey method. When conclusion was drawn there were it is seen that marketing channels in mango marketing, which helped to calculate total marketing cost, marketing margin, marketing efficiency and price spread. The constraints were also discussed with growers and suggested some suitable measures. This present study pertains to the agriculture year 2022-2023.

Keywords: Marketing Channels, Total Marketing Cost, Market Efficiency and Price Spread.

Introduction

The mango, *Mangifera Indica* , which belongs to family of Anacardiaceae, is one of the most important tropical and subtropical fruits of the world and is popular both in fresh and processed forms. It is called as the king of fruits on account of its nutritive value, taste, attractive fragrance and health promoting qualities. It is a delicious, exotic and nutritional fruit giving vitamins A and B to the human beings. In many languages it is called the mother of all tropical fruits and is the national fruits of India. It is general concern among the people that mango is a fruit for all, everybody consuming this fruit either a poor or a rich community. Mango has been in cultivation in India subcontinent for well over 4,000 years and has been the most favourite fruit since ages. Mango is nutritious and an excellent source of carotene as compared to other fruits. A 100gram of edible portion of the mango contains about 1,990 mcg of beta-carotene (vitamin A), which is much higher than the same in other fruits. Eating mangoes in the season may provide a store of vitamin A in the liver, sufficient to last for the rest of the year and highly beneficial for the prevention of vitamin A deficient disorders, Like night blindness. Mangoes, both ripe and unripe, are good source of Vitamin C. About 16 mg of Vitamin C is present in 100 grams of Mango. Ripe mango provides a good source of calories and supplies 74 kcal per 100 grams. Mechanization, diversification and commercialization of agricultural resulted in shifting of cropping pattern also contributed significantly to shifting of more area under production of mango. However, marketing and processing of mango have not picked up proportionate with the level of production. Further, supportive mechanism in the form of agricultural inputs, post – harvest infrastructure set up, such as packaging, pre colling cold storage, pack house, marketing system and institutional credit have not come up in proportion to the increase in production of fruit. The various commonly grown commercial varieties are Rani Nabab Pasand, Bimli, Bariah, Fazli, Golapkhas, Gopalbhog, Anars, Langra Surma Fazli, Chausa, Himsagar, Neelam, Dashehari etc. Recently introduced varieties are Mallika and Amrapali.

Material And Methods

2.1 Selection of District: Malda district of West Bengal was selected for the study. West Bengal compares 23district out of which Malda

Result And Discussion:

Channel wise description of each marketing channel observed on the basis of their share in the marketing of Mango:

District was purposely selected for research work. Total area of Malda district 3733 sq. km and number of Tehsil and Subdivision 13 and 2. Malda is popularly known as mango city not only in the state but all over India due to its varieties of mango.

2.2 Selection of Blocks: There are 15 Blocks in Malda District, Name of the blocks are **Englishbazar, Old Malda, Bamongola, Habibpur Gazole, Manikchak, Kaliachak – I, II, III, Harischandrapur – I, II, Chanchal – I, II. Ratua – I, II.** Among them **Ratua – I** Block was selected purposely for the research work.

2.3 Selection of Villages: A list of villages in **Ratua – I** Block was obtaining from the Block Office. 5 percent villages were selected randomly for study on the basis of research work.

2.4 Selection of Respondents: A list of all respondents of Mango growers was obtained from village Panchayet in all selected villages. 10 percent respondents were selected randomly for study on the basis of land holding capacity.

2.5 Selection of Market: Primary and secondary market was selected randomly for data collection. **Ratua Krishak Bazar and Baharal Bazar** are the main Market for Ratua in Malda district, Where Mango are assembled for sale and distribution was selected purposely.

Tools Used for Analysis:

Marketing Cost: The total cost incurred on marketing by various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of commodity till it reaches the ultimate customers.

$$C = CF + CM1 + CM2 + CM3 + \dots \dots \dots CMN$$

Where, C = Total Marketing Cost,

CF = cost paid by producer,

CM1=cost incurred by 1st middleman.

Marketing Efficiency:

Marketing Efficiency= Consumer Price / Total Marketing Cost

Price Spread: It is defining as the difference between the price paid by consumer and the net price by the producer for an equivalent quantity of farm produce. It is expressed as percentage of consumer's price.

Price Spread = (consumer price – net price of producer) / consumer price

CHANNEL I

Table 3.1: Price spread of mango in channel I:

Sl. No	Particulars	Price / Qtls
1.	Net price received by producer	3400
2.	Cost incurred by the producer	
a.	Packaging cost	20
b.	Packaging material cost	12
c.	Miscellaneous charges	145
3.	Total marketing cost	177
4.	Sale price of producer / purchase price of consumer	3577
5.	Price spread	4.94
6.	Producer share in consumer Rupee	95.24

CHANNEL II

Table 3.2: Price spread of Mango in channel II:

SI No	Particulars	Price / Qtls
1.	Net price received by producer	2400
2.	Cost incurred by the producer	
a.	Packing cost	20
b.	Packing material cost	21
c.	Transportation cost	27
d.	Loading and unloading charges	50
e.	Miscellaneous charges	60
3.	Marketing cost	178
4.	Sale price of producer / purchase price of commission agent	2578
5.	Cost incurred by the commission agent	
a.	Loading, unloading and repacking cost	55
b.	Spoilage and losses	42
6.	Marketing cost	97
7.	Margin of commission agent	155
8.	Sale price of commission agent / purchase price of wholesaler	2830
9.	Cost incurred by the wholesaler	
a.	Loading, unloading and repacking charges	73
b.	Grading and sorting charges	62
c.	Spoilage and losses	53
10.	Marketing cost	188
11.	Margin of wholesaler	192
12.	Sale price of wholesaler / purchase price of retailer	3210
13.	Cost incurred by the retailer	
a.	Loading and unloading charges	37
b.	Carriage up to shop	45
c.	Miscellaneous charges	30
d.	Spoilage and losses	40
14.	Marketing cost	152
15.	Margin of retailer	143
16.	Sale price of retailer / purchase price of consumer	3505
17.	Total marketing cost	1105
18.	Net margin	490
19.	Price spread	31.52
20.	Producer's share in consumer rupee	68.47

CHANNEL III

Table 3.3: Price spread of Mango in Channel III:

Sl No	Particulars	Price / Qtls
1.	Net price received by producer	4500
2.	Cost incurred by the producer	
a.	Packing cost	20
b.	Packing material cost	21
c.	Transportation cost	27
d.	Loading and unloading charges	50
e.	Miscellaneous charges	60
3.	Marketing cost	178
4.	Sale price of producer / purchase price of commission agent	4678
5.	Cost incurred by the commission agent	
a.	Loading, unloading and repacking cost	55
b.	Spoilage and losses	42
6.	Marketing cost	97
7.	Margin of commission agent	175
8.	Sale price of commission agent / purchase price of Retailer	4950
9.	Cost incurred by the retailer	
a.	Loading and unloading charges	37
b.	Carriage up to shop	45
c.	Grading and sorting charges	75
d.	Miscellaneous charges	30
e.	Spoilage and losses	66
9.	Marketing cost	253
10.	Margin of retailer	137
11.	Sale price of retailer / purchase price of consumer	5340
12.	Total marketing cost	840
13.	Net margin	312
14.	Price spread	15.73
15.	Producer's share in consumer rupee	84.27

Table 3.4: Marketing efficiency of Mango in different marketing channel:

Particulars	Units	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
Consumer purchase price		3577	3505	5340
Total Marketing price		177	1105	840
Net price received market intermediaries	Price/ Quintal	3400	2400	4500
Marketing efficiency		20.21 %	3.17 %	6.36 %

Table 3.4 reveals about the marketing efficiency of different marketing channel in which marketing efficiency of channel I by conventional method is 20.21 %, marketing efficiency of channel II is 3.17 % and marketing efficiency of channel III is 6.36 %

Summary And Conclusion:

For Mango Marketing and by providing adequate institutional credit the performance and efficiency of mango marketing in the Malda district could be improved. Study reveals about the price spread of different marketing channel in which price spread of CHANNEL I by conventional method is 4.94, price spread of CHANNEL II is 31.52 and spread of price in CHANNEL III is 15.73. The total marketing cost in CHANNEL I is 177, in CHANNEL II the total marketing cost is 1105 and in CHANNEL III the total marketing cost is 840.

The Marketing Efficiency of CHANNEL I is 20.21 %, in CHANNEL II marketing efficiency is 3.17 % and in CHANNEL III the marketing efficiency is 6.36 %.

From the analysis it is clear that the present marketing system for Mango had not been an efficient one. Lack of organization,

inadequate transport facilities, high price fluctuations in market, lack of storage facilities and many other problems faced by the farmers and marketers. If the measure suggested were adopted by the policy makers, the government and the farmers, it might be hoped that the future of mango marketing and the economic conditions of both growers and marketers would flourish.

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